

resorting to special breeding to increase restoration ability. The superior yielding ability of the hybrids over the checks was found to come from increased total biomass and increased panicle weight, with almost the same level of harvest index. Harvest index and panicle weight, however, can be further increased by increasing spikelet fertility in hybrids, which can ensure an additional increase in total grain yield. ■

Studying heterosis for grain yield and its components in hybrid rice

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Heterosis in hybrid rice was studied in the 1995 wet season under irrigated conditions. Some 22 F_1 hybrids developed by using cytoplasmic male sterile lines IR58025A, PMS1A, PMS2A, PMS3A, and PMS10A and 18 restorers were grown along with the standard variety HKR126 in a randomized block design with three replications. Each line was planted in a single row 3 m long. Spacing between rows and plants was kept at 30×15 cm. Observations were recorded for grain yield plant^{-1} , panicles plant^{-1} , grains panicle^{-1} , and 1,000-grain weight.

The standard heterosis of F_1 hybrids for these traits was calculated over HKR126. The standard heterosis was found to be significant for all four traits. It was both negative and positive for grain yield plant^{-1} (-0.57 to 54.75%), panicles plant^{-1} (-14.84 to 89.14%), and grains panicle^{-1} (-16.04 to 43.28%), and negative for 1,000-grain weight (-34.55 to -5.82%). Positive and significant standard heterosis was observed in 6 hybrids for grain yield plant^{-1} , in 12 hybrids for panicles plant^{-1} , and in 7 hybrids for grains panicle^{-1} . The hybrids PMS1A / Pusa 44-33 (54.75%), PMS3A / RP2151-40-1 (40.86%), PMS2A / IR 31802-56-4-3-3R (37.37%), IR58025A / IRON89-54 (36.48%),

PMS1A / RP2151-173-1-3 (33.21%), and PMS2A / Pusa 44-33 (32.86%) showed positive and significant standard heterosis for grain yield plant^{-1} , panicles plant^{-1} , and grains panicle^{-1} . ■

Standard heterosis of rice hybrids for yield and yield components

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The exploitation of hybrid vigor is widely recognized as the only readily available means to raise the genetic yield ceiling in areas where yields have already approached their potential. In this approach, developing highly heterotic rice hybrids with superior yield performance and evaluating them across environments are important. We assessed the performance of 10 promising rice hybrids to estimate the standard heterosis over popular medium-duration rice variety Prabhat for yield and yield components.

Significant differences existed among the hybrids for all characters studied, thus indicating considerable variability. Hybrids were of early to medium duration and had a semidwarf plant stature. Six hybrids had significantly higher grain yield over Prabhat. MTUHR2015 had the highest grain yield (5.65 t ha^{-1}), followed by MTUHR2002 (5.13 t ha^{-1}). The released hybrids APHR1 and APHR2 had the 4th and 5th positions, respectively. Though hybrids had long panicles with more spikelets panicle^{-1} , the expected grain yields were not realized because of spikelet sterility and lower grain weight.

The standard heterosis of hybrids for plant height was insignificant except in MTUHR2006, which showed a negative response (-17.8%). Similarly, MTUHR2020 and MTUHR2015 exhibited significant and positive heterosis for panicle length. All hybrids except MTUHR2006 exhibited a very high positive standard heterosis for number

of spikelets panicle^{-1} . This was reflected in the positive high heterosis for grain yield. All hybrids showed negative and significant standard heterosis for 1,000-grain weight because Prabhat had a bold grain with a high 1,000-grain weight of 32 g. Most of the hybrids possessed slender grains with lesser weight.

Heterosis is a highly cross-specific phenomenon. To use heterosis successfully to improve grain yield, parental genotypes need to have a high potential yield. We need to reduce spikelet sterility and increase grain weight to realize the effect of high heterosis for number of spikelets panicle^{-1} in rice hybrids. ■

Developing Pusa 5A, a stable indica CMS line with high outcrossing potential

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From available germplasm and breeding lines at IARI, we have identified Pusa 150-2, a maintainer with excellent agronomic traits. Pusa 150-2 is a high-yielding semidwarf indica variety with excellent grain quality.

When test-crossed with IR58025A, it produced F_1 progeny with 100% pollen sterility. The F_1 progeny was backcrossed to Pusa 150-2 and a population of approximately 750 BC_1 plants was raised. All plants showed 100% pollen sterility under the microscope but segregated for various agronomic characters. Thirty plants showing characters comparable with those of Pusa 150-2 were backcrossed. All the progenies were 100% sterile.

Fifteen of these progenies were selected for further backcrossing. All plants in the BC_3 population showed 100% sterility. Five of these populations showing close similarity to Pusa 150-2 were further backcrossed and the BC_4 population was raised. All five populations showed perfect pollen and

spikelet sterility. In the BC₅ also, pollen and spikelet sterility were maintained in the progenies. The CMS line derived from progeny 1 was named Pusa 5A.

The outcrossing potential of this line was evaluated against IR58025 A, PMS2A, PMS3A, and PMS10A using the respective B lines. Pusa 5A recorded a seed yield of 2.8 t ha⁻¹ vs 2.0, 0.6, 0.7, and 0.8 t ha⁻¹ of IR58025A, PMS2A, PMS3A, and PMS10 A, respectively. Pusa 5A had more tillers, longer panicles, more spikelets panicle⁻¹, and better stigma exertion than IR58025A. Pusa 5A may therefore prove to be a good alternative to IR58025A, the most popular cytoplasmic male sterile line used in India. ■

Field evaluation of thermo-sensitive genic male sterile lines

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The use of thermosensitive genic male sterility (TGMS) is well recognized in two-line heterosis breeding. The use of the TGMS system has several advantages over the cytoplasmic genic male sterility system, such as (1) its simple and efficient seed production system, and (2) its greater scope for enhancing heterosis because any genotype can be used as a male parent. To develop hybrids using the TGMS system, it is necessary to identify or develop lines that show a desirable transformation from fertility to sterility and vice versa.

We evaluated several TGMS lines that carried TGMS genes introduced from IRRI. Besides intensive study under field conditions for five seasons, starting in 1994, we made simultaneous individual plant selections in these lines. The TGMS lines were (1) IR68945-4-33-14, (2) IR68948-12-3-7, (3) IR68949-11-5-31, (4) IR68945-4-33-4-14, and (5) IR32364-120-1-3-2. Lines 1, 2, and 3 showed very good transformation between seasons. At Hyderabad,

during the wet season, the weather is unstable and daily mean temperatures below 25 °C occur frequently. The daily maximum temperature is 29 °C, which induces fertility in most of the IRRI-bred TGMS lines. During the dry season, however, the daily mean temperature is always >25 °C, with a daily maximum of >32 °C beginning in the second week of March, which induces sterility in most lines, including the selected lines 1, 2, 3, and 4.

During the 1995-96 dry season, 325 plant progenies of TGMS lines 1, 2, 3, and 4 were evaluated in two sets planted at 10-d intervals. The results showed that IR68945-4-33-14 still segregated for plant type, grain type, and sterility, whereas IR68948-12-3-7 and IR68949-11-5-31 were almost stable. Another line, IR68945-4-33-4-14, was uniform, but partially fertile, and appeared to be a very high-temperature sterile type. Plants showing stable sterility were selected and their stubble was planted in the 1996 wet season, in which all those lines transformed to fertility further confirmed their behavior. IR32364-120-1-3-2 did not set seeds in either season after 1994. Although the anthers were light yellow, they did not shed any pollen, which was >99% abortive type. Perhaps it is a very low-temperature fertile type. Lines IR68948-12-3-7 and IR68949-11-5-31, which also have desirable floral traits that influence outcrossing, will be used in hybrid rice breeding in the coming years. ■

Developing thermo-sensitive genic male sterile lines in rice

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The three-line method (A/B/R) of heterosis breeding is cumbersome and warrants development of alternate approaches to exploit hybrid vigor commercially in rice. Two-line breeding

is one such possibility that emerged following the chance discovery of photoperiod-sensitive genic male sterile (PGMS) lines and thermosensitive genic male sterile (TGMS) lines in China.

A study was conducted to identify a stable TGMS source from suspected and introduced TGMS lines under natural conditions. Thirty-eight lines were evaluated at Coimbatore (high temperature 38/23 °C) and at Gudalur (low temperature 30/16 °C) simultaneously during summer 1995. Pollen fertility in these lines was recorded during the flowering stage using I-KI (1%) solution. Panicles were bagged and spikelet fertility recorded.

Lines TS 15 and TS 16 showed 100% pollen sterility at Coimbatore and 55-80% pollen fertility at Gudalur. The sterile lines are maintained as stubble at Coimbatore for further evaluation in the wet season. These lines are also evaluated under controlled conditions to determine the critical sterility and fertility points of temperature. Crosses are also made simultaneously with agronomically superior lines to transfer the TGMS genes. ■

Male sterility and fertility behavior of suspected thermosensitive genic male sterile (TGMS) lines

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The male sterility-fertility response in thermosensitive genic male sterile (TGMS) lines was studied to identify their adaptability to different temperature regimes. Twenty suspected TGMS lines available at the Paddy Breeding Station, Coimbatore, were used for the study. The plants of these lines, which were completely male sterile during summer 1995, were tagged and observed for their male sterility-fertility behavior in the ratooned tillers during winter 1995 and summer 1996 by staining pollen grains with I-KI. Panicle development stages, from the